

Exploring Digital Information Literacy among Tribal Communities in Rural Areas of Majuli District, Assam- A key study

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Abstract

This paper investigates Digital Information Literacy (DIL) among tribal communities in the rural areas of Majuli District, Assam, aiming to assess their digital skills and identify barriers to improvement. The aim is to assess their digital skills and identify barriers to improvement. Researchers conducted structured, face-to-face interviews with 60 tribal respondents. Key findings show that 70% of participants own smart phones, 60% use the internet, and the same 60% have digital literacy skills. Additionally, 76% access the internet from home.

The study highlights the need for better infrastructure enhancement, digital literacy programs, and establishment of information centers to bridge the digital divide in these communities.

Keywords: Digital Information Literacy, Digital Divide, Information Access Tribal Communities, Rural Areas, Majuli District,

1.0 Introduction

Information literacy is like a beautifully wrapped gift—it sounds inviting but can be tricky to open. It's more than just reading or handling data; it's a lively, meaningful skill to navigate and use information in ways that go beyond the traditional ideas of literacy and information. The term "Information Literacy" first coined by Poul Zurkowski in 1974, he explained *"People trained in the application of information resources to their work can be called information literates. They have learned techniques and skills for utilizing the wide range of information tools as well as primary sources in molding information-solutions to their problems."* *"Information literacy ... faculty, librarians and administrators need tools to evaluate the information literacy abilities of students"* and that *standardized multiple-choice tests may come to predominate by default which "may not be well-suited to the task of evaluating higher-order skills"*. Dunn (2002, p. 28) Digital literacy means the ability to read and create content in important languages found in digital formats. This includes audio, video, images, SMS, MMS, and graphics. It involves using digital media to find and carefully assess information gathered from the internet. According to Bawden (2008), DIL is defined as the set of attitudes, understanding, and skills to handle and communicate information and knowledge effectively, in a variety of media and formats.

Majuli Island of mighty Brahmaputra River in Assam, India, is considered to be the largest river island of the world (Mahanta, 2001; Naik, 2002) it is home to over 153,000 people. Majuli is the location of the "Vaisnavite" shrines, sometimes referred to as "Satras," and Assam's unspoiled cultural legacy. As a result, over the past 400 years, the island has been a major destination for pilgrims. However, it is now well-known for having experienced flooding and significant bank erosion, two natural hazards. According to 2011 Census total population of Majuli is 167304, with 144 village. Among this population, 77,603 is Schedule Tribe, which is 46.38% . This includes most of Mising tribe, along with other ingenious communities like Deorikachari, Hazong etc. They are relatively isolated from technology. Poor infrastructure, limited internet access, and low digital literacy make it difficult for them to access digital opportunities. On this research paper our main objective try to investigate digital information literacy among the tribal community of Majuli District of Assam.

2.0 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Finding digital information literacy among tribes, with particular reference to Majuli district's rural areas, is the main goal of the current study. Its goals are as follows:

1. To determine how well tribal groups can recognize, locate, and analyze digital information.
2. To analyze the standards by which tribal cultures evaluate digital information in various formats.
3. To evaluate tribal groups' capacity to evaluate communications according to the accuracy and dependability of digital data in a range of digital formats.
4. To assess indigenous groups' choices for information access.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

A survey research method was used to carry out the investigation. Data was collected through simple random sampling. Based on the goals of the study, a structured questionnaire was created, and community members used the pre-made forms in English and Assamese Language. Tribal members from three chosen regions received a total of seventy questionnaires. All 70 responders filled out the surveys and sent them back for review.

For easier comprehension, the gathered data was collated and displayed using graphs and tabular data. Data analysis was done using statistical software R-4.5.1.

4.0 ANALYSIS OF DATA

Collected data through questionnaire from the 70 tribal's people from six different village of each from Majuli District Assam, have analyzed in following tables.

Table 1: Gender based total Distribution of the Respondent

Gender	Total no of Responded	Percentage
Male	43	61.42
Female	27	38.57
total	70	100

Here the Table 1 indicates that out of a total of 70 respondents, 43(61.42%) were male, followed by 27(38.57%) of the respondents were female. It shows that a majority of the respondents were male.

Fig 1- Age Group Distribution

Figure: 1- represent that the respondents i.e., 29% (20) are under 30 years, and 31% (22) respondents are in the age group of 35-45 years. 23% (16) belongs to age group 46-60 and 17% (12) are more than 60 years.

Table-2: Educational Status of Respondents

Education plays a vital role in shaping an individual's personality, reflects their intelligence and ability to access and utilize information sources. Based on the data collected on the educational status of the respondents

Sl. no.	Education qualification	Total No of Respondent	Percentage
1	up to Class V	7	10
2	up to Class X	19	27.14
3	up to Xi	25	35.71
4	graduate	15	21.42
5	Post Graduate	4	5
	Total	70	100

It was observed that the highest proportion, 10% (7 respondents), had completed education up to Class V. This was followed by 27.14% (19 respondents) who had completed up to Class X. Additionally, 35.71% (25 respondents) had done Class XI. 21.42% (15 respondents) educated up to graduate level, while 4.44% (2 respondents) had received education only up to the middle and primary school levels, respectively. Educated up-to Post Graduate level followed by 5% (4 respondents).

Table 3. Smart Phone an Internet Use

Sl no		Yes	%	No	%
1	Ownership of smart phone	49	70	21	30
2	Internet user	42	60	28	40

Below table shows that 70% people have ownership of smart phone, 60% are able to using Internet.

Table:4- Types of information need of respondents

sl no	Types of need	most often	%	often	%	sometime	%	rarely	%	Total
1	Agriculture	5	7	23	32	30	43	12	18	70
2	Career	25	35	13	18	10	14	22	31	70
3	Entertainment	57	81	6	8	5	7	2	2	70
4	Govt. scheme	35	50	9	12	16	22	10	14	70
5	Health	20	28	12	17	17	24	21	3	70
6	NEWS	34	48	21	30	11	15	4	5	70
7	online shopping	48	68	12	17	4	5	6	1	70
8	Weather	8	11	10	14	12	17	40	57	70

The data illustrated in the Table 4 related to opinion of the respondents about types of information they went to seek. On the basis of respondent's preference, it can be seen that most of respondents 81% most often need information to entertainment, followed by for online shopping (68%), NEWS (48%), health related (28%). However, most of the respondents (35%) were often need information related to Agriculture which is (23%), NEWS (30%), Career (18%), entertainment (6%), health (17%). Whereas most number of the respondents (57%) were rarely need the information related to weather , Career (31%). Bellow Figure-2 shows types of information need of respondents.

Fig-2: types of information need of respondents

Table:5 - Purpose of the information response

sl no	Purpose	most often	%	often	%	sometime	%	Rarely	%
1	agriculture products	2	3	16	22	35	50	18	24
2	Education Related	29	41	16	22	18	25	7	12
3	For Curriculum	9	13	6	8	32	46	23	33
4	Health Sector	12	17	23	32	28	40	7	11
5	Job Related	25	35	18	26	10	15	17	24
6	Political Related	24	34	19	27	12	17	15	22
7	Travel and tourism	7	10	12	17	29	42	22	31

The results indicate that the majority of respondents use information primarily for educational and job-related purposes. People also seek information to stay informed about local, national, and political affairs; discover new travel destinations; and exchange digital content to keep themselves and their peers updated. Additionally, they use information to improve agricultural productivity and increase household income, watch sports or play online games for entertainment, recharge mobile phones and televisions to access new content, learn about government welfare schemes, and engage in digital transactions to support a cashless economy. Many respondents also use information to prepare for competitive exams, search for new jobs, and contribute to both community and personal development by staying connected with the wider world.

Table- 6 Availability of digital information Technology of Respondents

sl no	Digital Technology	Yes	%	No	%
1	Computer	4	6	66	94
2	Laptop	26	37	44	62
3	Smart Phone	52	74	18	26
4	Tablet	8	11	62	89
5	Television	56	80	14	20

Availability of digital information technology show that 56(80%) of respondents accepted television available for access digital information, followed by 52(74%) Smartphone, 26 (37%) Laptop, 8 (11%) tablet, 4(6%) of respondent have computer.

Table – 7: App used for Access Digital Information

sl no	Search engine name	Mostly used	%	Some time used	%	Never Used	%
1	Whatsapp	58	82	8	11	4	6
2	Youtube	62	89	2	9	6	8
3	Google Chrome	40	57	15	21	15	21
4	duck duck go	0	0	18	26	52	74
5	Telegram	22	31	35	50	13	19

Here mostly used Youtube, whatsapp and Google Chrome for access digital information. Less people used Duck-duck go which is one of the secure search engines for access digital information. Its because of their lack of awareness.

5.0 Suggestions

Here some suggestion is for improving Digital information rate for Tribal Communities in Majuli District, Assam:

1. Digital Libraries: Need to establish digital libraries in rural tribal villages with affordable ICT, Wi-Fi, and broadband facilities.
2. Government Scheme Resources: Provide digital information on beneficiary schemes such as E-district, E-Pehesan, in local languages and accessible formats.
3. Digital Literacy Program: Conduct frequent training like PM Kausal VikashYojona, E-kranti, DISHA, MyGo, E-pathshala, DigiLocker and hands-on workshops to enhance digital skills.

6.0 Conclusion

Digital information literacy promotes social, economic, political, cultural, and professional development and is essential for lifelong learning and personal development. The findings show

a moderate level of digital information literacy among tribal communities in Majuli of Assam. They have significant access to smart phones and use the internet. However, challenges like slow connectivity and poor infrastructure highlight the need for targeted digital literacy programs and better access to information resources to close the digital gap. It provides a forum for self-expression, creativity, innovation, and entertainment—all of which are critical for learning, interacting with others, and pursuing career goals.

Digital information literacy in tribal communities faces challenges from economic limitations, limited access to higher education, slow and costly internet, network issues, a lack of public libraries and offline information systems, content primarily in English, and technological barriers. Proposed solutions include online training modules, skills mapping, needs assessments, tailored training programs, long-term plans, and decentralized efforts to improve digital literacy.

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